

**THE SUBTLENESS OF THE NARRATIVE PATH: A RELATIONSHIP
OF LITERATURE AND HISTORY IN THE CHRONICLES "FEBRUARY
4, 1890" AND "JANUARY 19, 1891" BY DOMÍCIO DA GAMA**

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Abstract: Literature is a form of expression of aspects and cognitives; it is the discussions that promote the scope of e history, some approximations, others what they promote. Taking advantage of this proximity, the proposed work relates an articulation of the subtleties of the narrative path of Domício da Gama chronicles entitled "4 de Fevereiro de 1890" and "19 de janeiro de 1891", with the intention of answering the question of A literature and the story, although they intersect, can they establish a harmonious relationship during the narrative process? For this, the objective is: to analyze how it is possible to establish a narrative subtlety between the intricacies of literature and history in Gama chronicles, more specifically, to identify the literary and historical intersection in the chronicles; and highlight the current relationships in the chronicle on literature and history. For this, the text "Trópicos do discurso" by (White, 1994), "história e Literatura: Algumas Considerações" by (Borges 2010), "Literatura e História: reflexões acerca das possibilidades de diálogos entre as áreas" of (Farias; Rocha and Pereira, 2020). Therefore, it can be seen that literature, through the chronicle genre, a very intimate dialogue with the existing relationships in the social environment, with the insertion of imaginary elements, however, helping, through a simpler language, an understanding of the elements of the historicity that predominate in the cultural and social environment.

Keywords : Literature; History; Chronicle; Gamma Home.

INTRODUCTION

The discussions that revolve around literature and history do not raise recent debates, but dating back a long time, thus, many were the discussions that permeated, and that currently still permeate the paths of literature and history, promoting a relationship of approximation, and distance from these two major areas of study.

History, in the perspective of study, has gone through a series of devaluations related to not reaching the *status* of science, this because there were no proper methods of analysis,

unlike other areas of research, in addition, many historians did not support the approach of history with literature, this is because as FARIAS mentions; ROCHA E PEREIRA (2020), history is the representation of the past, the instrument that designates events through oral or written records, that is, based on factual elements, showing the facts that took place in that space delimited by the historian, and exempting itself from the relations with the fictional that are deriving from literature.

However, literary studies also went through some problems, mainly related to its definition, as shown in the text by RENÉ WELLEK and AUSTIN WARREN (2003), with the chapter "*The nature of literature*", which proposes a definition for literature; about these studies it is initially mentioned that everything that is printed is the manifestation of literature, with no distinction for what belonged to another area of knowledge, thus, everything related to the history of civilization was included in literary studies, but, such a perspective would be intrinsically related to the object of study of history, that is, there would be a conflict between what belonged to literary studies, and what belonged to history.

Despite the existence of these approximation relations between these two areas of cognition, it is clear that both have specific research objects, in addition to establishing different analyzes on the same social bias, but still having a contributory relationship to the understanding of both.

It is still worth noting that both history and literature provide discourses that respond to social concerns, as highlighted (FARIAS; ROCHA E PEREIRA 2020, p. 2) "we see them as narratives that respond to questions, expectations, desires and fears". about reality, which offer the world as a text", therefore, are quite evident and important relationships for social relationships.

The historical and literary interrelationships

The interdisciplinarity relations between literature and history have reached a new level, and denote a fundamental importance for the social environment, as both allow a series of debates about what is configured in the collective sphere, through the delimitation of time, or space, despite be established between different areas of study, but which in turn maintain an intertextual dialogue.

The historian, HAYDER WHITE (1994), in his book "*Trópicos do discourse*", chapter "*historicism, history and imagination*" mentions that figurative discourses provided

factual mentions, as well as historical discourse makes use of these elements of progressive codifications, since there are elements of two levels of meaning, as evidenced:

The historian – like any writer of discursive prose – shapes his materials. It can shape them in such a way as to adapt them to a “structure of preconceived ideas” [...] or in such a way as to conform them to a “preconceived selective point of view” equal to that of the novelist in the role of narrator of a story . But in either case, his account of the phenomena under examination will develop on at least two levels of meaning, which we can compare to the manifest and latent levels of a dream or to the literal and figurative levels of imaginative literature in general. (WHITE, 1994, p. 124)

The author shows that, as in other writings related to a prose structure, there is this relationship of interpersonal meaning, the historical text is not immune to such elements, the two levels mentioned are the data, the information described, and secondly plan the interpretation of these data.

The distinction between its two textual elements (historical and literary) is based on the difficulty of distinguishing the occurrence of these two levels, differently from what concerns literature, which is already expressed from the subjective relationships that permeate the author, as well as the reader.

The authors FARIAS, ROCHA and PEREIRA (2020) emphasize that history is understood as an intertextual construct, that data are instruments of interpretation by historians. In other words, the historian's discourse is part of a combinatorial order, like what happens in the language axis through paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationships ¹.

These relationships can be understood through the existing plurilingualism and exposed by Bakhtin, in which he mentions the constitutive elements in humorous speeches, but which can also be extended to other discursive textual elements, let's see:

This attitude of the author towards language as a current opinion is not immobile, it is always subject to the condition of some live movement, of a sometimes rhythmic oscillation: sometimes more, sometimes less, the author parodically deforms some moments of “common language”, or abruptly reveals its inadequacy to the object. Sometimes, on the contrary, as if in solidarity with her, only keeping a minimum distance, and, from time to time, making her own “truth” resonate directly in her, that is, completely confusing his voice with hers. (BAKHTIN, 2010, p. 108)

To visualize this relationship, it is necessary to observe the table below that carries some highlighted linguistic utterances:

¹They are axes of linguistic organization, in which the syntagmatic is defined as the axis of combination, and the paradigmatic the axis of the choices of signs. These axes are responsible for the functioning of the language, based on the relationships of choices.

O Milagre Econômico

Na área econômica, o país crescia rapidamente. Este período que vai de 1969 a 1973 ficou conhecido com a época do Milagre Econômico. O PIB brasileiro crescia a uma taxa de quase 12% ao ano, enquanto a inflação beirava os 18%. Com investimentos internos e empréstimos do exterior, o país avançou e estruturou uma base de infra-estrutura. Todos estes investimentos geraram milhões de empregos pelo país. Algumas obras, consideradas faraônicas, foram executadas, como a Rodovia Transamazônica e a Ponte Rio-Niterói.

Porém, todo esse crescimento teve um custo altíssimo e a conta deveria ser paga no futuro. Os empréstimos estrangeiros geraram uma dívida externa elevada para os padrões econômicos do Brasil.

FONTE: Só história.

The textual elements highlighted in the text evidence this insertion of the historian's subjective view, which are demarcated from the selection of words, and from some aspects of generalizations. In this way, the presence of the issue of the two levels of intentionality is perceived, these relationships result from the refractory manifestations that are established through semantic associations, textual composition, or the author's axiology. Every text is formulated by elements that refer to a purpose/intentionality, the literary text exposes its pluri-significant relationships, and also correlates the literariness.

Although history has these “controlled fiction” relationships ², it still plays an important informational role on the social context of a given time, already in the literary environment, this dialogue is evidenced and expressive about some literary manifestations, such as the chronicle genre, that maintains a link with the historical context.

The literary chronicle and historical relations

The chronicle in the Brazilian territory had a very important relationship, since it is from it that we have an initial note about the space of what would later be called Brazil, despite starting from a unilateral perspective, since there is the point of view of the Portuguese, but there is no perspective of the first inhabitants. It was through the landscape relationship that the chronicler's enthusiasm was awakened, in documenting the visual captures, offering an excellent scenario, with the wealth of details, for what would be considered the birth certificate of Brazil.

However, much has been discussed whether through the writing of Pero Vaz de Caminha's letter there was the inauguration of the literary process, despite it having a great

²Term used by Sandra Pesavento in “História & História Cultural” (2003).

historical relevance, in addition to denoting an importance even in poems, and other narratives, showing then that there was a first structuring in the literary environment, as reported by SÁ (2005).

It is through directly experienced observations that it becomes possible to discuss recurring associations, this, because there was a careful relationship in describing the circumstances, the same care that exists in the field of history, as stated:

Hence the care in reaffirming that he writes after having gone to land “to walk there with them and learn about their way of life”: direct observation is the starting point for the narrator to be able to record the facts in such a way that even the more ephemeral to gain a certain concreteness. This concreteness assures permanence, preventing them from falling into oblivion, and reminds readers that reality – as we know it, or as it is recreated by art – is made up of small moves. (SÁ, 2005, p. 6)

The basic principle of the chronicle is based on the relationship of recording the circumstantial, making it possible to establish a certain connection with the historical discourse, in which it was shown through a medium and neutral plan, the historian's object of study is based on the field of events that dissolve into microlevels, because according to WHITE (1994) it refers to the set of strategies that will be traced for the mention of a certain event, as an example the creation of the chronicle, which is produced from a particular event.

Within this relationship, it is evident that every text has a specific and segmented language according to its purpose, and to the audience it will be intended for, in this way, it is necessary for both the literary chronicle and the historical text to establish a relationship of situationality. (time/space).

The historical discourse, as well as the discourse inserted in the chronicle genre, are established through a metadiscursivity, as it makes clear:

Precisely because it is aporetic, or ironic, with respect to its own adequacy, discourse cannot be governed solely by logic. Because it is always escaping the domain of logic, constantly asking if logic is adequate to capture the essence of its themes, the discourse always turns to metadiscursive reflexivity. That is why every discourse is always about the discourse itself and it is about the objects that make up its theme (WHITE, 1994, p. 17).

This relationship establishes boundaries to think about the existing connections in the historical environment, how the discursive union is established in this environment, in addition to the very strategies that lead the reader to have certain perceptions, BORGES (2010) emphasizes that the intellectual and cultural field is shown through from different

segments, considerations of rules, and relationships established from the social and cultural environment.

Thus, it is necessary to identify the multiple linguistic, cultural, and social aspects that are evidenced in the historical and literary discourses, as Borges records:

In the broad universe of cultural goods, literary expression can be taken as a form of social and historical representation, being an exceptional witness of an era, since it is a sociocultural product, an aesthetic and historical fact, which represents human experiences, habits, attitudes, feelings, creations, thoughts, practices, concerns, expectations, hopes, dreams and diverse issues that move and circulate in each society and historical time. (BORGES, 2010, p. 98)

In other words, it shows through the narrative path the contributions to social and historical representation. Regarding the chronicle genre, it has a varied structure, allowing the insertion of several subjects, and was produced to be linked in the journalistic environment, in which everyday events are narrated, facts that happened in certain locations and are related within the context temporal, in addition to having expressive characteristics that make it impossible to classify it as a closed language genre.

Still related to the chronicle, CANDIDO (2003) mentions that this genre is always helping to establish and reestablish the dimension of things, through a more simplified language, showing the amplitude that is transmitted through the kid and reflected in it a greatness, a beauty or an unsuspected singularity through the subtlety in its approach.

The chronicles were able to help in the visualization of a society different from the one experienced in Brazil, so that it was understood by the great mass, thus, the constancy in the publications made possible the diversified perceptions around the writing of Gama, it allows the insertion of varied visual aspects to your writing, in addition to captivating the reader.

Thus, transforming that environment that predominated a plurality, and a meaning prevailing. Through the chronicler's craft, its importance for the sharing of information is noted, so journalism has benefited so much from this genre, especially in the period of effervescence in the nineteenth century and early twentieth century.

The study of the involving narrative subtleties in the chronicles of Domício da Gama

The articulations that permeate the field of literature and history are recurrent elements, but that sometimes allows a departure due to the conception of these two areas of study, especially when literature has the possibility of moving between the various elements

that are established by other areas. knowledge, and still show its characteristics, and make possible meanings to the social environment.

The chronicles to be analyzed, “4 de Fevereiro de 1890” and “19 de janeiro de 1891” , were produced for the newspaper *Gazeta de Notícias* , and published in the column “De Paris”, which Domício da Gama was responsible for and which occupied the pages of *Gazeta de Notícias (RJ)* during the period from November 23, 1888 to January 29, 1893.

The chronicle carries as its title the date of its publication “4 de Fevereiro de 1890”, it encourages discussions of the subtle path involved in the transition between literary and historical aspects. As can be shown:

Christmas week runs calm and uneventful. It doesn't rain, it isn't cold, there is even sunshine from time to time, a sample sun, which hides just behind the opaque curtain of fog. Sometimes clouds gather, and from the dark sky it begins to sift a fine flour of snow, which does not last.

Underneath this pale blue or gray sky, it seems that these days there is a break in the work for History. Constipated emperors, kings and heads of state sneeze and cough in chorus with their ministers. [...] that was enough for *influenza* to serve as a pretext for those who want to dodge the tedious task, for all the laziness that only the lack of a reasonable, credible justification prevents from manifesting. (GAMMA, 1890)

Through this quote, it is possible to perceive the expressed manifestations of the literary discourse explored by Domício da Gama, where he begins by describing how the Christmas week in Paris takes place, through the recreational aspects, in addition to emphasizing that novelties are scarce, due to the calamity caused by the flu virus, expanding his approach to climate relations, which takes place in an atmosphere without many events, only those that occur by natural means, as he reports: even the snow that falls is thin, without enthusiasm for durability.

Another recurring element in Domício da Gama's writing is based on the insertion of visual aspects, expressing himself through figures of speech that are indispensable during the chronicler's description. It is through relations of inertia that the field of history is added, since this climatic relationship led to a dispensation from visits by political figures, this because “emperors, kings and heads of state constipated sneeze and cough in chorus with their ministers”. .” (GAMA, 1890), that is, due to the epidemic situation that devastated Europe.

Thus, the narrative course is based on the relationships in which the *influenza flu* began to be used as a pretext by some people. In addition to later showing how these relationships affected some areas of French popular entertainment.

The language used to show the relationships that plague European society is of great perspicacity, bringing together a relationship of the real, with the bias of literariness, mixed with a refinement of irony, this because it is necessary to take some care with the message that it wants to convey to the reader, as he reveals:

The approach, however, must seek to understand how the particular and inventive reception of a singular reader, a listener or spectator, is enclosed in a series of complex and related determinations – the effects of meaning aimed at by the very devices of writing; the uses and appropriations imposed by the forms of representation of the text; the competencies, categories and conventions that govern the relationship of each community with the different discourses (BORGES, 2010, p. 102)

And in this perspective, the relationships determined by the chronicle, as well as by the literature itself, enable some determinations, and that allows a plural relationship between the chronicler and the reader. Since according to CANDIDO (2003), the chronicle does not intend to last in time, thus, it does not need to use a far-fetched language, and that offers a scenario wrapped in exaggeration, but it can use a simpler and closer language. to the popular, in addition to the fact that this relationship is perceptible in the chronicle, which narrates a punctual event, and arising at that time.

The same is determined in the chronicle “*January 19, 1891*” . This chronicle has a peculiar narrative, initially showing the compositional relationships that permeate objectivity and subjectivity, as seen:

The cold north wind is deafening: deaf, we pay more attention to what goes on inside us, which the spectacle of the world creates and which we accompany in its epic career, from shadow to shadow, from the dawn of [...³] erasure by absorption in the created. But the cold north wind is numbing: the spirit also clothes itself and freezes, drawing a dark *cach-nez* of boredom and selfishness up to the eyes. Pilgrims' visions can now pass outside the windows covered in glass and wooded in the ice: the vision that interests me most, cold and apathetic, is the luminous storm that the air currents produce passing through the red-hot gold caves at the bottom. from the fireplace. That is silent and suggestive; it has everything you can dream of in color and movement, and the breath that consumes the ember in a caress is the habit of the sun (GAMA, 1891, p. 251)

Domício begins by narrating the aspects prevailing in the space, the climate, and what this caused in the chronicler himself, showing the appreciation of the sensitive dimension, the findings of the impression on various planes, whether sensory or visual. Mainly because he is the most affected by climate change, since he is “a poor tropical person” as he highlights.

³Illegível no journal

In this way, it is possible to show that literature has an indisputable autonomy, portraying some aspects present in the social environment, in which the chronicler establishes a predominant relationship with the icy winds that ravaged the Parisian population, and his poor experience in experiencing temperatures of this level. , since he is used to the tropical climate prevailing in Brazilian lands, still making a comparison between the crime of passion, and the animal and unconscious crime, that time was committing. Domitius still mentions the predominant aspects of his personal hygiene, compared to Parisian customs. A question is then asked to the reader:

If not to crime, to contempt – the bilious form of the bad feelings that anger arouses. Being so far from the exuberant outpourings of enthusiasm that anger arouses. Being so far from the exuberant effusions of enthusiasm, necessary for those who need to interest the distracted, what can the subjects of the Parisian chronicle of these last days seem to me, if not pettiness, banalities, songs with irritating refrains, what relevance can events have? poorly drawn against a dull, gray, neutralizing background? (*GAZETA DE NOTÍCIAS*. Rio de Janeiro, n. 19, 19 jan. 1891, p. 1)

Thus, it can be observed that the narrative course transcends without any fear, the chronicler has a narrative freedom to reproduce his thoughts, to propose questions that are evidently a concern of himself, not hiding his own relationships through the narratological nuances.

It is through this relationship of independence that literature makes use of, being able to enjoy the past, the documentary aspects, among other techniques to be explored at its whim, in addition to highlighting its own characteristics.

The narratological evidences expressed in the chronicle genre are instilled in the linguistic aspects, in which they can be explored from different aspects, BORGES (2010) mentions that the literary discourse manifested in texts, involve narrative modalities that are articulated in their own characteristics, through questions that are preponderant in the social environment and that permeate various literary spheres.

Through these more subtle relationships that involve the writing of the literary text, there is the insertion of the aspects arising in the social space.

“At present, with the advances of studies in both areas of knowledge, when one thinks that the one who writes literary texts is historically positioned and influenced by the moment of their writing, it is understood that literature can indeed be considered a historical fact, taken as different representations of History, since literature is essentially language” (FARIAS; ROCHA E PEREIRA, 2020, p. 5)

This relationship is very apparent through the plot of the chronicle, in which it uses the context that prevails at the time the chronicler is writing, as well as dialoguing with historical aspects of the time. As can be seen through the chronicles being analyzed.

The narrative of the chronicle *4 de Fevereiro de 1890* mentions an epidemic in Europe, caused by *influenza*, with consequences for the country, not only related to the political environment, but to various social spheres, due to such circumstances, the work of historians had been interrupted, as the meeting of the political representatives would not take place. And still highlighting how the population behaves in the face of such events, as shown:

Constipated emperors, kings and heads of state sneeze and cough in chorus with their ministers. And the malaise of the rulers allows the ruled a political rest, which everyone needs to celebrate Christmas and to take care of colds and bronchitis. [...] That was enough for *influenza* to serve as a pretext for those who want to dodge the tedious task, for all the laziness that only the lack of a reasonable, credible justification prevents from manifesting. (*GAZETA DE NOTÍCIAS*. Rio de Janeiro, n. 33, 2 fev. 1890, p. 1)

However, the chronicle remains in contact with the current events in Paris, not limited to mere descriptions, but still expressing its judgment about the problems, but using the subtle and narratological relationships of literature.

The chronicle “ *January 19, 1891* ”, despite starting the narrative in order to express the sentimental aspects, there is a narratological break, something that is pertinent within the genre itself, and resulting from a questioning made by the chronicler himself, in this way there is a historical approach based on the election of the president of the war minister council, which is soon fragmented to the approach of the philosophical opinion expressed in the newspaper, about the war.

However, an important change in the approach to the chronicle's structure is visible, to contemplate the various subjects that insert social relations, which are not only predominant in the European space, but also extending to the Brazilian one, since the chronicler establishes a parallel between Paris and Rio de Janeiro through the news that are issued. Through the image it is possible to visualize how the historical contexts are inserted in the chronicle:

Fig. 1. Chronicle January 19, 1891 .

Source: Digital Newspaper Library of the National Library.

Through the linguistic resources of punctuation, and small dialogic reflections, the narrator exposes the whole context, showing the events and positioning himself in the face of situations that cause him discomfort. Thus, it is possible to perceive that the text is an overview of the micro-narrative, as it shows historical relationships through the prism of a chronicler, in addition to enabling a new way of exploring the contexts of multiple experiences.

This issue of micro-narrative dialogues with aspects of micro-story, as it allows for a small-scale study that provides connections with other stories on larger scales, as mentioned by Levi:

Of course, it is immediately obvious that even the most seemingly insignificant action, such as someone going out to buy a loaf of bread, really involves the much larger system of grain markets around the world. And only a paradoxical and significant distortion of perspective would suggest that the commercial life of a village is of no interest beyond its significance on a local scale (BURKE, 1992, p. 137).

Thus, it shows that through elements at small scales a meaningful core is possible that correlates with a larger story. Literature provides these studies through its detailed elements during narrative subtlety. As mentioned:

In addition, literature appropriates not only the past, but also documents and techniques from the historical discipline, such as the device of creating the “ reality

effect”, approached by Barthes, as a modality of “referential illusion”, with the multiplication of concrete notations destined to carry the fiction with a weight of reality (CHARTIER, 2009, p. 24-5, 27-8, apud BORGES, 2010, p. 99).

Literature despite having its characteristics demarcated by fiction, it still has autonomy to represent the past/present experienced by the chronicler. Through the records, the chronicler has total independence to express himself in the face of the events that are being narrated, the reader of the chronicle also has the same autonomy, since literature creates an effect of reality, which allows the 'referential illusion', in addition to that, the narrative process of the chronicle allows the inclusion of linguistic methods, such as the addition of figures of speech.

WHITE (1994) even mentions that the historian's discourse is structured with the insertion of some of these elements, and it is still worth noting that there is a debate about these historical representations, in which some are based on analytical elements, and others on the narrativist, the chronicle, is inclined towards this second option.

That is, despite the text being configured with the perspective of the creator/artist/chronicler, as we go back to the context of history, an increasingly collective presence is noticed. In the creative process of the work, all spaces are conditioning factors that influence production. Due to these characteristics, CANDIDO (2006) mentions that it is necessary to investigate the role played by the creator of the art, in addition to his position in the social scale, because in this way, it is possible to understand all the constituent elements of the text structure, as well as its value in society.

In view of what is exposed, the chronicler has a relevant role in literature, in the social environment, as he observes with a critical eye the reality that surrounds him, transferring his perceptions to the written modality, for the contact with the other. In this sense, the chronicle expresses the particularities of a people, all through the narrative of space, clothing, frustrations, as well as the prevailing political relationship, which has the social environment as its epicenter, which is one of the chronicler's contributions to the Brazilian population.

Final considerations

Through all the exposed aspects, it became evident that literature despite having its own characteristics, it still relates and provides a new research investigation for history, this through the narrative subtleties that are intrinsically linked to the structure of the elements. literary texts, more specifically, through the studied genre, the chronicle.

In view of these elements, (BORGES, 2010, p. 108) mentions that literature, whether it is expressed in its multiple genres, “presents itself as a poetic configuration of the real, which also aggregates the imaginary, imposing itself as a source category. special to the cultural history of a society.” Thus, making significant contributions to popular knowledge, in addition to proposing new debates on issues little evidenced from the historian's discourse.

Regarding the genre, what makes the chronicle even more realistic is the richness of details, in which it expresses its experience in the face of the new, in the descriptions it is possible to flow imaginatively over the space in which it was inserted, in addition to awakening. a curious and critical look at the themes addressed, which can be contemplated through a variety of contents, such as micro-narrative.

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